

Spatiotemporal dynamics and influencing factors of ecosystem service trade-offs in the Pearl River Delta region

Yucheng Zhang^{*1}, Dafang Wu^{†1}

¹ School of Geography Science and Remote Sensing, Guangzhou University, Guangzhou 510000, China

GISRUK 2024

Summary

Understanding ecosystem service trade-offs and their influence is crucial for sustainable socio-ecological development. Using InVEST model, RMSE, and redundancy analysis, we assess spatiotemporal patterns of carbon storage (CS), water yield (WY), habitat quality (HQ), and soil conservation (SC) in the PRD, quantifying trade-off and revealing influencing factors. The results show that: (1) CS and WY increased, HQ and SC decreased from 2000 to 2020. (2) The trade-off strengths between CS-WY, CS-SC, and HQ-WY increased, while those between SC-HQ, SC-WY, and CS-HQ decreased. (3) Temperature, elevation, and rainfall are the main factors influencing the trade-offs.

KEYWORDS: ecosystem service; trade-off; redundancy analysis; Pearl River Delta region; decision optimization

1. Introduction

Ecosystem services refer to the natural conditions and utility of ecosystems that sustain human well-being, and are the benefits that humans obtain directly or indirectly (LI *et al.*, 2013). However, due to the complexity of ecosystem services and the diversity of human needs, it is difficult to maximise the benefits of ecosystem services at the same time, i.e. there are trade-offs between services (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). As the contradiction between human demand for ecosystem services and their preservation becomes more and more obvious, clarifying the trade-offs between different services and exploring their driving mechanisms to provide reference for human well-being have become the focus of current research (Wu *et al.*, 2023).

Li *et al.* measured the strength of ecosystem service trade-offs in the Yangtze River Delta urban agglomeration, revealed the key driving factors, and suggested that policy makers should focus on food production while improving the quality of the ecological environment (Li *et al.*, 2022). Yin *et al.* found that there is heterogeneity in the trade-offs among WY, NPP, and SC in different climate zones, and that different measures should be taken to protect the environment in a targeted manner (Yin *et al.*, 2024).

The Pearl River Delta (PRD) region is one of the densely populated urban areas in China with the highest level of urbanisation and the greatest intensity of development and construction (Liu *et al.*, 2023). Since the reform and opening up, a series of ecological problems have come to the forefront with the rapid development of urbanisation in the PRD region, leading to an intensification of the conflict between ecosystem service functions. Therefore, there is an urgent need to investigate the spatial and temporal evolution of ecosystem services in the PRD region, and to clarify the trade-offs between different services and the factors affecting them. The research results are expected to be used to support regional ecological governance and maintain the sustainable development of social-ecological systems.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

* 2112201079@e.gzhu.edu.cn

† wudafang@gzhu.edu.cn

The PRD is situated in the southeastern part of Guangdong Province, featuring flat topography, and it encompasses a total of nine cities (**Figure 1**)

Figure 1 Location of the study area

2.2. Methods

In this study, we quantitatively assessed the amount of four ecosystem services, namely CS, HQ, WS and WY in the PRD region in 2000 and 2020 with the help of the InVEST model, and quantified the strength of the trade-offs between the different ecosystem services with the use of the RMSE, which is based on the Vegan package of the R language to judge the relationship between the ecosystem service trade-offs and the environmental factors (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2 The workflow of this study

3. Result

3.1. Spatial and temporal changes in ecosystem services

Table 1 shows changes in carbon stocks, habitat quality, soil retention, and water production in the Pearl River Delta (PRD) region from 2000 to 2020. Carbon stocks and water production increased,

while habitat quality and soil conservation decreased.

From 2000 to 2020, ecosystem services in the PRD region remained spatially stable, with discernible changes (**Figure 3**). Carbon stocks exhibited a gradient, lower in the center and higher in the surrounding areas, notably in the northwest and northeast.

Habitat quality and carbon stocks show a consistent gradient of "high in the north and low in the south." Soil conservation is mainly characterized by low values, scattered with a few high-value areas in the northwest and northeast, indicating a general pattern of higher values in the center and lower values in the surroundings. Water yield in the PRD region from 2000 to 2020 displays a noticeable spatial difference, generally following a pattern of "high in the south and low in the north."

Table 1 Statistics on CS, HQ, SC and WY and Changes in the PRD Region, 2000-2020

Year	CS	HA	SC	WY
2000	5.446×10^8	0.617	1.165×10^{10}	5.724×10^8
2020	5.544×10^8	0.550	1.136×10^{10}	5.788×10^8
2000-2020	1.79%	-10.88%	-2.48%	1.11%

Figure 3 Spatial Distribution of Ecosystem Services in the Pearl River Delta Region, 2000-2020

3.2. Spatial and temporal evolution of ecosystem service trade-offs

Utilizing the RMSE index to assess trade-off strengths (**Figure 4**), we observed trends in the interactions between ecosystem services from 2000 to 2020. Trade-offs between carbon stocks and habitat quality decreased during this period. High-value areas were concentrated in the west and northeast, while low-value areas expanded from the central part of the Pearl River Delta (PRD) to its surroundings. Predominantly, high-value areas were located in the southeast coastal region, and low-value areas were distributed in the northwest and east inland sections. The two decades witnessed an increase in high-value areas and a decrease in low-value areas. Trade-offs between carbon stock and soil conservation were characterized by sporadically distributed low values in the central study area. The strength of trade-offs between soil conservation, habitat quality, and carbon stock decreased from 2000 to 2020. Spatially and temporally, soil conservation and habitat quality exhibited a "low in the middle and high in the surroundings" trend, with low values expanding in all directions over the 20-year period. The distribution of soil conservation and water yield showed a "low in the southeast and high in the northwest" trend, with a decrease in the area of low values. Habitat quality and water yield were concentrated in the center of the study area. The trade-off and synergistic relationship between habitat quality and water yield increased from 2000 to 2020. High values were mainly distributed in the northwest, northeast, and central coastal areas, while low values were prevalent in the south and west, showing a significant increase in high values over the past two decades..

Figure 4 Spatial distribution pattern of ecosystem services trade-off intensity in the PRD region in 2000 and 2020

3.3. Factors influencing the strength of ecosystem service trade-offs

Figure 5 displays RDA ranking results, revealing elevation, slope, and NDVI's positive correlations with CA-HQ and HQ-SC trade-off strengths in 2000, and negative correlations with CS-WY and WY-SC. Similarly, slope and elevation positively correlate with CS-SC and HQ-WY trade-offs, while NDVI shows a negative correlation. Rainfall and population density positively correlate with CS-WY, WY-SC, and CS-SC-HQ-WY trade-offs, but negatively correlate with others. Temperature positively correlates with CS-WY and WY-SC, and negatively correlates with others. In 2020, elevation, slope, and NDVI positively correlate with CS-HQ, HQ-SC, and CS-SC, and negatively correlate with HQ-WY, CS-WY, and WY-SC trade-offs. Temperature and population positively correlate with HQ-WY, CS-WY, and WY-SC, and negatively correlate with others. Rainfall negatively correlates with HQ-WY and CS-SC, but positively correlates with others. Ordination diagrams show HQ-WY having the longest arrow in 2000, indicating the greatest influence of selected variables on the HQ-WY trade-off. In 2020, selected variables exert the greatest influence on the WY-SC trade-off.

Figure 5 depicts the explanatory power of driver factors on trade-off strength. In 2000, temperature has the greatest influence (39.83%), followed by elevation (30.96%), with population, NDVI, and slope showing comparable influence at 26.86%, 25.9%, and 24.71%, respectively. Precipitation is the least

influential at 10.24%. In 2020, NDVI is the most influential factor (41.76%), followed by temperature (37.45%). Elevation and rainfall exhibit similar influence at 35.74% and 31.93%, while slope and population have lower influence at 27.73% and 26.57%, respectively.

Figure 5 RDA ranking of impact factors and ecosystem service trade-offs, 2000 and 2020

4. Acknowledgements

National Natural Science Foundation of China, "Optimisation of Urban Land Allocation Based on Ecological Services under the Perspective of Stakeholders: A Case Study of Guangzhou City" (41771096).

References

- LI, C., JIE, Z., ZHUANG, Z. & GU, S. (2022), "Spatiotemporal dynamics and influencing factors of ecosystem service trade-offs in the Yangtze River Delta urban agglomeration", *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, Vol. 42 No. 14, pp. 5708-5720.
- LI, S., ZHANG, C., LIU, J., ZHU, W., MA, C. & WANG, J. (2013), "The tradeoffs and synergies of ecosystem services: Research progress, development trend, and themes of geography", *Geographical Research*, Vol. 32 No. 08, pp. 1379-1390.
- LIU, W., ZHANG, F., WEI, Y. & ZHAO, F. (2023), "The balance between ecosystem services supply and demand in the Pearl River Delta Urban Agglomerations area", *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, Vol. 43 No. 11, pp. 4461-4472.
- WU, W., ZENG, H., GUO, C., YOU, W., XU, H., HU, Y., WANG, M. & LIU, X. (2023), "Spatial heterogeneity and management challenges of ecosystem service trade-offs: a case study in Guangdong Province, China", *Environmental management (New York)*.
- YIN, Y., LI, H., ZHANG, M., WANG, L. & JIANG, J. (2024), "Spatial heterogeneity of ecosystem service trade-offs in different climatic regions and its driving factors: A case study of the Sichuan-Yunnan-Loess Plateau ecological barrier zone", *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, No. 01, pp.
- ZHANG, B., MIN, Q., JIAO, W., E, S. H., LIU, M. & YANG, L. (2021), "Research progress and perspective on ecosystem services trade-offs", *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, Vol. 41 No. 14, pp. 5517-5532.

Biographies

Yucheng Zhang, Master's student of the School, Guangzhou University, is mainly engaged in the research of ecosystem service function change and land use carbon emission.

Wu Dafang, Associate Professor, School, Guangzhou University, mainly engaged in the research of arable land protection, land resource management and other directions.